

History of American Community Survey Use in Federal Surveys and Information Products

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Abstract

The American Community Survey (ACS) is a leading source of timely and accurate demographic and socio-economic data for both small areas and small populations. Given its annual production cycle, other federal surveys and other tailored information products have benefited from the use of the ACS in several ways. This includes frame development, follow-on surveys, bench-marking, and small-area applications, to name a few. This paper will discuss the history of ACS data use in federal surveys and other applications, including its foundation as a replacement for the decennial census long-form as well as how its use has evolved to exploit the increased timeliness that the ACS has to offer.

Key Words: frame, follow-on surveys, blended data, visualizations, modeling

1. Introduction

The American Community Survey (ACS) is the largest demographic survey administered by the U.S. Census Bureau. It annually samples 3.54 million housing unit addresses and all persons living within them as well as approximately 170,000 persons living in group quarters. The final interviews are processed, tabulated, and published in the form of 1-year and 5-year estimates available in September and December respectively of each year on the Census Bureau website. In addition to these fixed tabulations, the Census Bureau also releases a Public Use Microdata Sample (PUMS) file as part of its standard data products that allows data users to create custom tabulations, run models, or other analyses that support their needs.

However, these standard data products only scratch the surface of all the applications of the ACS by data users from across the spectrum including those at the federal, state, and local level. The ACS is used as input to design other surveys, to create new information products that blend multiple data sources together, and as inputs to model estimates.

In this paper, we will highlight some of these data uses, focusing on the federal sector. While not an exhaustive list, we will attempt to provide examples of a broad swath of uses that illustrate its historical use by federal agencies including the Census Bureau itself.

2. Background

The current design of ACS grew out of a deepening desire in the 1980s to have more frequent data than what was available from the once a decade decennial census long form. The long form provided incredibly rich and detailed information about our

*Any opinions and conclusions expressed herein are those of the author and do not reflect the views of the U.S. Census Bureau.

nation and her communities that was not available from any other federal source. However, it was typically published approximately three years after the census and was not updated for another ten years after that. Thus, the age of the data ranged from 3–13 years old at the time of its use, including any secondary uses in dependent data products.

When long-term decennial census projects were being proposed in the early 1990s for the decade leading up to the 2000 census, work finally began on alternatives to the census long form for collecting and producing these vital statistics on a more frequent basis. The initial goal was to have an alternative in time to replace the long form in the 2000 census. To this end, the ACS was developed and began testing in 1995 with data collection starting in 1996 for a group of four counties. However, the goal of replacing the long form in 2000 proved to be too ambitious and thus the long form was retained for Census 2000. The revised goal was to have the ACS fully functional by 2003 which would be in time for planning the scope of the 2010 census. After some final tests, the full implementation of the ACS was achieved in 2005. Thus, 2000 was the last census which utilized a long form as it was discontinued for the 2010 and future censuses.

During these early years, many applications were considered how an annual survey of this magnitude could be used to provide not just more timely statistics but to strengthen the federal statistical program as a whole (Alexander, 1994). In this paper, we will explore both some of those early ideas as well as a selection of applications that have been implemented since that time.

3. Using Unit-Level ACS Data for Other Programs

One key application that was envisioned in Alexander (1994) was the ability to link ACS data to other data sources at the unit level. A key enabling technology to realize this potential was the development of the Master Address File (MAF). The MAF would provide a continuously updated address frame rather than rebuilding it from scratch in time for each decennial census (U.S. Census Bureau, 2009). This was viewed as a cost-saving measure for the census but it also had the potential to greatly simplify the sampling for ongoing demographic surveys including the proposed ACS. Indeed, the ACS planned to only use a unit frame without an area frame or building permit frame as was used by other demographic surveys at the time. There was an added benefit, however, of developing the MAF in that it would allow direct linking of the ACS to other surveys once they fully transitioned to sampling entirely from a unit frame. In addition, they also envisioned linking administrative records to the addresses on the MAF which would allow for easy linkage of address-level administrative records to the survey data.

They saw the MAF as key step to facilitate follow-on surveys for rare populations, potential blended data products, and more streamlined data collection processes to name a few. In this section, we detail some of these unit-level applications of the ACS.

3.1 Follow-on Surveys

One use of the ACS has been to use the interviewed ACS universe as a frame for follow-on surveys. This is particularly useful for small populations that can be

identified via their ACS responses. While the regulations over the sharing of Title 13 has prevented this option from being available to other agencies directly, agencies can and have contracted with the Census Bureau to conduct surveys directly. There are limitations placed on using the ACS in this manner, however, to avoid over-burdening ACS respondents with many follow-on surveys. These restrictions are governed by the Interagency Council on Statistical Policy Subcommittee on the American Community Survey based on guidelines outlined in their charter (Interagency Council on Statistical Policy, 2023).

In general, the survey must demonstrate that the target population is a very rare subset of the household population; leads to a large cost savings to the Federal Government; and that the size and geographic coverage of the ACS is critical for the follow-on survey. Typically, the cost reduction for such a survey comes from the elimination of a costly screening survey which would otherwise be needed to identify the target population. It is worth noting that the requirement stipulating a reduction in cost to the Federal Government effectively limits the use of the ACS for follow-on surveys to federally sponsored surveys only. Private-sector surveys are not eligible.

We present below two follow-on surveys based on the ACS. The first example, the Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander National Health Interview, was a one-off survey without a regular production schedule to be repeated. The second, the National Survey of College Graduates, does have a regular production schedule and regularly uses ACS data for subsequent sampling frames.

3.1.1 NHPI National Health Interview Survey

The goal for the 2014 Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander National Health Interview Survey (NHPI NHIS) was to collect the same data as the 2014 NHIS but restricted to households containing one or more NHPI residents (National Center for Health Statistics, 2017a). The general NHIS was not sufficient for this task as only 100–250 NHPI households were in the NHIS in a given year. For this reason, a new instance of the survey was proposed whose sampling frame would come from households in the ACS that contained one or more NHPI residents (National Center for Health Statistics, 2017b). This significantly increased the final sample size to approximately 3,000 households in the final interviewed sample. Without using the ACS in this manner, the survey would have required a large screening sample to achieve an interviewed sample of this size.

In addition, the timeliness of the ACS was very important in order to have as current of a record of the occupants as possible. This was necessary in order to minimize sample loss due to the NHPI residents moving out of the household, the entire household moving, etc. The ACS offers some strong advantages over the census in this regard in that a new basis for a follow-on survey can come at any point in the decade. With the long form before it, it is likely that such a survey could become untenable more than a few years away from the census because of the increased risk of sample loss.

3.1.2 National Survey of College Graduates

The National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics administers the National Survey of College Graduates (NSCG) on a biennial (every two years) basis in order to gather characteristic data on the universe of college graduates in the U.S. More precisely, the NSCG samples from the population who have a bachelor's degree or higher, are not institutionalized, and are less than 76 years old. For this population, the NSCG collects data on demographics, educational history, employment status, field of degree, and occupation (National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics, 2021). When the survey first began, the decennial census long form was used as a sampling frame as it contained the most comprehensive national inventory of persons falling into the target population. Thus, once the population was identified among the long-form respondents, the NSCG sample could be selected as a follow-on survey once a decade (in 1993 and in 2003). The NSCG then used this sample for several panels to follow the individuals through the decade. This approach was not without its limitations, however, as the further away from the sample selection they got, the more likely there was to be dropouts from the original sample.

Once the ACS had reached full implementation, the NSCG transitioned to using the ACS as its sampling frame. Using an annual survey like the ACS posed new opportunities for updating the sampling frame more often than was possible with the long form. After considering options ranging from keeping the same design to selecting a new sample for each panel, they finally settled on a rotating panel design. This design reuses some of the sample cases from the preceding panel while adding new sample cases from a more recent ACS data year. This balances timeliness with the added reliability of leveraging the overlap between panels (much like the monthly Current Population Survey). For more information on how this transition was made, see Fesco et al. (2012).

3.2 Linked Data

Linking ACS data to other sources typically requires the data to remain housed at the Census Bureau because of the legal restrictions placed on the data. Thus, both examples of linked datasets presented here come from the bureau although frequently they involve outside partners.

3.2.1 Mortality Disparities in American Communities

The Mortality Disparities in American Communities program (MDAC) links ACS person data to mortality outcomes from the National Death Index (NDI) produced by the National Center for Health Statistics and Medicare / Medicaid information from the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS). The database also includes information on proximity to hospitals, parks, and other local neighborhood and environmental characteristics.

This linkage enables an administrative follow-on study that can examine the demographic, social, and economic characteristics by cause of death for those individuals in the ACS who have deceased. Indeed, the analysis can either study different incidences of causes of death within a single demographic group or to study the incidence rates across various demographic group for a single cause of death. The vintages of data currently being used for the project include the 2008

ACS and the 2008–2015 NDI and CMS data. For more information see U.S. Census Bureau (2015).

3.2.2 Frames Project

In 2020, the Census Bureau launched the Frames Project. This project is unlike the other items described so far as it is neither a survey nor information product on its own. Instead, it is a series of linked unit frames that sources information from administrative records, censuses, and surveys. The vision is to establish three frames including a geospatial frame, a demographic frame, and a business frame. These frames could then be used to design new surveys where the information is used to define the sample design or the sampling frame, to augment surveys that only need to ask the information that is not available already on the frame, or to create blended data products with existing surveys. Given the size and breadth of the ACS, the survey will make a large contribution to this project, in particular to the demographic frame. For more information on this exciting work see Ratcliffe (2021).

4. Using Area-Level ACS Data for Other Applications

Using area-level ACS data in new information products is much more widespread due to ease of access and availability of existing products. Unlike the uses of unit-level data, gaining access to area-level data requires no special access permissions as the ACS standard products provide a wealth of data for a wide array of summary levels. In some cases, however, if the pretabulated products do not meet a data user’s need, they can either utilize our Public Use Microdata Sample (PUMS) files or request a special tabulation. Where the PUMS files meet the user’s geographic and statistical reliability requirements, this option provides a no-cost alternative to requesting a special tabulation.

4.1 Improve Estimation in Other Surveys

The ACS can be very helpful in making other survey data more representative either via a specific non-interview adjustment of as part of a more general calibration within the weighting methodology. Some key examples of this include the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS) of health-related surveys conducted by the CDC and the Household Pulse Survey (HPS) conducted by the Census Bureau.

4.1.1 Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System

The BRFSS is a random digit dialing survey that collects information on a wide range of topics (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, 2022a). After the sampling stratum design weights are calculated, the weights for the survey are constrained to an eight-way marginal totals using iterative proportional fitting, also known as raking. Besides margins that include various combinations of base demographics estimates, the BRFSS also adjusts for the distribution of education, marital status, and tenure which are sourced from the ACS PUMS files (U.S. Census Bureau, 2021a). In their application, they rake to

the distributions from the ACS applied to demographic estimates for counts of age, sex, race, and ethnicity that are drawn from a separate source (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, 2022b).

4.1.2 Household Pulse Survey

The HPS (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023c) similarly uses the ACS in both the calculation of housing unit weights and person weights. For the housing unit weights, it controls the estimated number of occupied housing units (and hence the number of households) to the published ACS 1-year estimate for the same measure. Here the use of the ACS is critical because the Population Estimates Program only publishes estimates of total housing units and does not publish estimates of housing units broken out by occupancy status.

The ACS is also used in the person weighting to control the estimates of educational attainment by age and sex to the corresponding ACS estimates. Like the BRFSS, a separate source is used to control to the base demographics which, in this case, comes from the Population Estimate Program. For more information see U.S. Census Bureau (2023e).

4.2 Denominators in a Variety of Prevalence Rates

Frequently, prevalence rates are calculated using different data sources for the numerators and denominators. For example, vital statistics records may provide a numerator, such as the number of deaths, but not a corresponding denominator for the total population. The Population Estimates Program provides the official estimates of the population during non-census years and includes estimates by race, Hispanic, age, and sex. However, these estimates do not always correspond to the populations of interest for a given application. In these situations, the ACS is often used as a source to estimate these populations.

For example, the National Center for Health Statistics uses ACS-based population estimates to calculate mortality rates for Hispanic sub-groups (e.g., Central or South American, Cuban, Mexican), Asian sub-groups (e.g., Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino), marital status and education. All of these categories are examples where official population estimates from the Population Estimates Program do not exist and so the ACS is the next best source for these estimates. For a published example of these types of rates, see tables I-5 through I-7 in Xu et al. (2021).

4.3 Current Uses of ACS in Population Estimates Program

In the years that do not include a decennial census, the Census Bureau's Population Estimates Program produces the official population estimates for the nation, states, counties, and functioning minor civil divisions and incorporated places (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022b). While most of the data sources used to produce these estimates come from the previous decennial census and a variety of administrative record sources, the ACS is also used to help estimate certain components of the estimates.

While the methodology for producing the population estimates has become more complicated since 2020 with the introduction of the "blended base" for the Vintage 2021 estimates and beyond, the methodology for producing the county-level data

by demographics is still generally a cohort component method that tracks changes from the base by births, deaths, and migration (including both net international and net domestic migration as appropriate). Vital statistics records typically provide the key demographic data necessary to estimate births and deaths by demographic characteristics. However, sources to estimate migration do not always have this information. In addition, for estimating net international migration, subnational migration information may also not be available.

For this reason, the ACS is used to both add demographic characteristics to the estimated migration as well as to estimate the subnational distribution of where the immigrants settle within the U.S. The ACS is also used to help estimate the flow of U.S. residents between Puerto Rico and stateside. The ACS is particularly well equipped for this use case as one can use the residence one year ago question information collected from residents of Puerto Rico who respond to the Puerto Rico Community Survey (the ACS as implemented in Puerto Rico) and those who migrated from Puerto Rico to stateside and respond in the ACS. This aids in being able to measure gross flows in each direction between stateside and PR. For additional details see U.S. Census Bureau (2022a).

5. Data Visualizations and Blended Data

One area for information products, both public and private, that has exploded with the broad use of the internet is the creation of data visualizations including blended data. In some instances, visualizations are created dynamically using, for example, the Census Bureau API (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023b) that allows ACS and other census data to be pulled via a structured URL. In other instances, the data may be downloaded in summary files, transformed, and then presented in the desired format. In addition to presenting data from a single survey, blended data applications are also becoming more prominent where data from multiple data sources, including both survey and administrative data, can be presented for a given area. This expands the realm of analyses that are possible compared to using a single data source. In this section, we present two examples of data mapping software that are maintained by federal agencies.

5.1 National Environmental Public Health Tracking Network

The “National Environmental Public Health Tracking Network” by the CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023) allows for side-by-side mapping of a vast array of environmental, health, and demographic data including many characteristics taken from the ACS. One benefit of using the ACS over the census in this application is that you can better match the reference period for the demographics taken from the ACS with the year that the other data source was produced. This provides a more appropriate comparison when investigating relationships that may exist between the data. The ACS provides data on “Age of Housing”, types of housing units, internet access, and commuting information just to name a few. Data are available for counties and tracts as well as custom created geographies that meet certain size thresholds.

5.2 My Community Explorer

In 2020, the Census Bureau worked with other partners to create a data hub that presented data from multiple sources to aid communities trying to identify vulnerable areas and how to respond during the COVID-19 pandemic. From this early work, the bureau developed a broader tool to help communities plan with the My Community Explorer tool (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023d).

This mapping tool currently is able to show ACS data, economic data from the County Business Patterns and Non-Employer Statistics, along with a new product, the Community Resilience Estimates. The Community Resilience Estimates use ACS estimates and Population Estimates from the Population Estimates Program to produce an easily understood metric to communicate the vulnerability of an area to the impacts of disasters, including COVID-19 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023a).

In addition to these data, overlays are automatically generated for active hurricanes and the potential to add other disaster information. This tool can help federal, state, and local planners how to concentrate their efforts in responding to a disaster situation. In the past, this type of information may have been created as a reaction to a disaster. Having the tool already stood up and working for all areas allows critical information from the ACS and other sources to be used much earlier in the planning stages.

6. Using Area-Level ACS Data for Modeling Applications

6.1 Enhancing Existing Survey Estimates

One early application of the ACS that was envisioned in Alexander (1994) was the ability to use the ACS to enhance the other specialized demographic surveys. So far, these applications have mainly been the topic for research but have not been implemented. Two examples are provided below.

6.1.1 Improving Small Area Estimates of Disability

In the work by Maples and Brault (2013), they study the feasibility of leveraging the size and general questions on disability asked by the ACS in order to improve the more detailed estimates provided by the Survey of Income and Program Participation (SIPP) albeit based on a smaller sample size. In this work, they utilize only the ACS and SIPP data in a regression projection estimator. This is one example of how the larger, but more general, ACS could be used to improve the estimates for a smaller survey. In a subsequent paper, You et al. (2014) investigate alternative models, including a bivariate model with a Fay-Herriot component and a measurement error model, which also use administrative record data for social security and disability income as covariates.

6.1.2 National Health Interview Survey

Further research on improving the estimates for smaller surveys was explored by Carolina Franco and William R. Bell (2022) with applications to both SIPP and the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS). In this work, bivariate small area estimation models are used to improve the more detailed estimates for the more

detailed survey using the more general estimates obtained from the ACS without using any other data sources. The goal for this research was to show the benefits possible from a methodology such as this even when relevant administrative record data may not be available and thus may be able to be used for a broader set of applications. In this way, it differs from the work of You et al. which also made use of auxiliary data to improve their estimates of disability. Again, while this work has not been implemented, it shows significant promise on how the ACS can be used to improve the estimates coming from other surveys.

6.2 Specialized Products

6.2.1 Small Area Income and Poverty Estimates

The goal of the Small Area Income and Poverty Estimates (SAIPE) is to provide annual single-year estimates of income and poverty all U.S. states and counties as well as estimates of school-age children in poverty for all school districts. This product is especially important because besides improving the overall accuracy of the income and poverty estimates through the use of models, it also provides single-year estimates which are more timely than the five-year estimates that would be available from the ACS for the same small geographies.

To accomplish this, since 2005 the SAIPE program combines ACS 1-year estimates at the state and county level for income and poverty and develop models using a mixture of administrative record data and survey data to create a regression model estimate. The final SAIPE estimate is then a composite estimate using a shrinkage estimator that places greater emphasis on the ACS direct estimate in larger geographies and greater emphasis on the modeled estimate for smaller, less reliable, geographies. This improves the overall precision of the estimates for all areas, including smaller states. In addition, it uses the ACS 5-year estimates to provide additional data to strengthen small areas.

Prior to 2005, the SAIPE program used 1-year estimates from the Current Population Survey Annual Social and Economic Supplement (CPS ASEC) for the current data and census long-form data to aid the small areas. The availability of the ACS provided a significant improvement in the reliability of the 1-year direct survey portion of the estimation as well as more timely data compared to the census long-form data that was previously used. For more information, see U.S. Census Bureau (2022c).

6.2.2 Small Area Health Insurance Estimates

The goal of the Small Area Health Insurance Estimates program, or SAHIE, is to produce model-based estimates of health insurance coverage for counties and states (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020a). This allows the comparison of geographic and demographic variation in coverage as well as variation by income levels as determined by a variety of state and federal assistance programs.

Since 2008, the SAHIE program has used the ACS single-year estimates of health insurance coverage as a primary input to the model, replacing the use of CPS ASEC estimates much the same way that the SAIPE program also switched from CPS ASEC to the ACS. In addition to the ACS, many other sources of data are used

including the bureau’s County Business Patterns, Demographic Population Estimates, and decennial census. The modeling also makes use of several administrative record sources including aggregated federal tax return information, SNAP benefit data, Medicaid participation data, and the Children’s Health Insurance Program Participation data. For more details on the methodology, see U.S. Census Bureau (2020b).

6.2.3 Section 203 of the Voting Rights Act

Section 203 of the Voting Rights Act requires that certain states and political subdivisions provide language assistance if it is determined that there is a sufficient population or proportion of the population that meet the criteria specified in the legislation (U.S. Census Bureau, 2021b). The determination of which states and political subdivisions and for what language minority groups had previously been determined using the 1980, 1990, and 2000 decennial census long-form data. This was due to both the characteristic information required and the small jurisdictions for which estimates were needed. However, even using census long-form data, the variance on the estimates needed to make these determinations could be high for the small language minority groups covered by the statute.

When the ACS was first used for the making the Section 203 determinations in 2011, the Census Bureau researched how it could improve upon the ACS 5-year direct estimates by incorporating the 2010 Census data and also employing small area estimation techniques to improve the accuracy of the estimates. After evaluation, these modeled estimates formed the basis for the first determinations using the ACS. See Joyce et al. (2014) for additional details. All subsequent determinations, including the 2016 and 2021 releases, have used modeling to create the estimates used in the determinations. However, in both 2016 and 2021, decennial census data was not used out of concerns about timeliness (in 2016) and because of availability (in 2021). Thus the methodology was adjusted for subsequent determinations to use ACS data exclusively while still improving the precision of the estimates. The methodology for 2021 can be found at Slud et al. (2022).

7. Closing

The ACS has a wide range of applications in the federal sector as well as other government sectors and private uses. In this paper we illustrated some of that breadth. While the ACS was expected to inherit many of the applications of the decennial census long form that preceded it, its timeliness has also led to its adoption for many other applications where the static nature of the long form throughout the decade was not well suited.

This includes not limiting follow-on surveys to the beginning of the decade when the census data is most current. Those surveys can now use the ACS at any point in the decade offering greater flexibility than what we had previously. The ACS has also replaced the use of other annual demographic surveys for use as control totals or denominators for rates because of its greater reliability compared to the smaller surveys. Finally, it also offers greater geographic coverage and detail than the current surveys which opens up new or otherwise improved estimates for a range

of blended data and modeling applications. For all of these reasons the ACS has become a foundation for other applications across the federal sector.

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